

Opportunities for increasing nutrition in food aid initiatives supported by surplus food supply

This report has been prepared for the FixOurFood Commission in collaboration with FareShare Yorkshire

Acknowledgements

We are especially grateful to the food aid initiatives who generously shared their time, experiences, and reflections during interviews. Their openness and commitment to supporting communities have been central to this work. We also extend our thanks to FareShare Yorkshire for their collaboration and invaluable support in facilitating access to networks, offering practical insight into surplus food redistribution, and contributing to the research process.

In addition we would like to recognise the support of the Public Health team at North Yorkshire Council who supported this work as part of the Food for the Future action plan. This report would not have been possible without the contributions of all those working tirelessly to improve food access and nutrition in our communities.

This report presents examples of interventions that have supported nutritional security in food aid initiatives and can be used to stimulate ideas for enhancing nutritional security. It should, however, be noted that there are social, cultural and environmental differences between food aid initiatives, and interventions often need to be contextualised to ensure their appropriateness.

Cite document as: Jackson, D. Williams, J., Newman, R., Stewart, S., Morris, B. Black, F., Pettitt, R., Barringer, P., Fazey, I., (2025). *Opportunities for increasing nutrition in food aid initiatives supported by surplus food supply*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17177258>

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Food aid initiatives were largely founded in response to urgent need during the pandemic and cost of living crisis to ensure that every person had access to emergency food relief. Rising levels of poverty in the UK have meant that food aid has shifted from emergency relief to a longer-term, systemic feature of community support.

Surplus foods redistribution is a key feature in delivering food aid, and organisations like FareShare play a key role in intercepting and redistributing surplus foods to food aid initiatives. By communicating with food aid initiatives, FareShare has seen that there are limitations to providing nutritional security in surplus food supply chains.

As a result, FareShare Yorkshire collaborated with the FixOurFood Commission to take a systematic approach to exploring how nutritional security can be better enabled in surplus food supply chains. Research involved exploring existing research and communicating directly with food aid initiatives to understand the challenges and opportunities for strengthening nutritional security in food aid initiatives that use surplus foods.

Key findings:

- **Surplus food is unpredictable and nutritionally inconsistent.** Donations depend on retail and manufacturing overproduction, seasonal gluts, or stock nearing expiry. This leads to variability in type, quality, and quantity. This often results in high volumes of processed foods, and insufficient supply of fresh, protein-rich, or culturally appropriate items.
- **Food aid initiatives lack infrastructure and capacity.** Many operate with limited storage (particularly chilled/frozen), irregular funding, and small volunteer teams. This makes it difficult to safely store fresh food, tailor parcels to dietary needs, or invest in initiatives like cooking education.
- **Nutrition is rarely a primary goal.** Most food aid initiatives are focused on meeting urgent hunger needs. While many recognise the importance of nutrition, they lack the time, training, or resources to systematically prioritise it.
- **Wraparound and inclusive services increase impact.** Initiatives that offer additional support (such as cooking classes, financial guidance or social support) show greater potential to support food literacy, independence, and dignity. However, wrap around services are hard to sustain because of resource constraints.

Summary of recommendations:

- **Policymakers** - Prioritise nutritional security in local strategies by embedding measurable nutrition outcomes. Recognise and support wider poverty alleviation efforts to prevent the need for emergency food aid.
- **Funders** - Provide long-term, flexible funding that supports food literacy programmes, essential infrastructure, and collaboration across organisations.
- **Surplus Food Suppliers** - Enhance the nutritional quality of redistributed food by increasing fresh and high-protein options while reducing excess ultra-processed items. Promote the donations of quality foods by implementing an award system to donors (i.e. in date, nutritious foods rank highly).
- **Food Aid Initiatives** - Adopt blended food access models and integrate nutrition into service design using layouts, education, and skills support.

Why do we need to explore nutrition in surplus food supply?

FareShare Yorkshire recognised that nutritional security is sometimes restricted within surplus food redistribution. In collaboration with FixOurFood, they sought to explore this challenge using a systems approach that placed food aid initiatives at the centre.

The aim was to better understand the real-world enablers and constraints that shape how nutrition is supported in practice. Insights were gathered through a literature review, an online survey, and in-depth interviews with food aid initiatives across the Yorkshire region.

The report begins by outlining the context and drivers of household food insecurity in the UK, with a focus on its nutritional impacts. It then examines the role of surplus food and alternative food access models in addressing food insecurity, while highlighting key challenges around nutritional adequacy. Findings from the literature, survey, and stakeholder interviews are then explored to develop a set of actionable recommendations for policymakers, funders, surplus food, and food aid initiatives.

By focusing on nutritional security, rather than food access alone, this report contributes to a more holistic understanding of how surplus food can be used not only to alleviate hunger but to promote healthier, more resilient communities. It is intended for use by food policy teams in local authorities, health and well-being professionals, funders of food aid initiatives, and organisations involved in surplus food redistribution or frontline food provision.

Understanding food insecurity and surplus food use

What is household food insecurity and nutritional insecurity?

Household food insecurity is a significant and growing problem in the United Kingdom (UK) (Boyle & Power, 2023). It relates to household ability to access quality, varied, desirable and nutritional food. It also considers impacts on health as well as social and cultural preferences (Hardcastle & Caraher, 2021). The prevalence of household food insecurity in the UK is debated and is different depending on the source quoted. According to the Department for Work & Pensions (DWP), household food insecurity is 11% of the UK population (Francis-Devine, 2024), but The Food Foundation (third sector organisation) states it is 15% (The Food Foundation, 2024) and wider research has suggested it's as high as 24.3% (Yau et al., 2020).

There is a common consensus that household food insecurity largely stems from inadequate financial capacity (Douglas, 2023; McRae & Westwater, 2023; Taylor et al., 2024). However, barriers to accessing food can be more complex (see Table 1 for examples). These barriers can also be related to wider systemic issues such as: the implementation of austerity measures throughout and following the 2008 financial crisis; welfare reform, Brexit and the weakening pound; real-terms growth in food prices compared with expanding inequalities and lower real-terms incomes; and recent macroeconomic and geopolitical shifts (Strong, 2021).

Table 1: Examples of barriers limiting the accessibility of and access to food.

Barriers limiting the accessibility of	Barriers limiting access to
The price of food & inflation such as: supply issues (i.e., poor harvests, Brexit, warring), fuel & energy prices, profiteering & the cost-of-greed crisis etc (Francis-Devine et al., 2024).	Low and/or unstable income - simply unable to afford diet or sudden, unexpected financial hardship: households forced to prioritise spending on other bills (Stone et al., 2024).
Proximity issues, i.e., distance to shops or store location (Wolfson et al., 2019).	Transit barriers: inability to physically access the shops (especially for rural or disabled households) (Bose, 2025).
Temporal issues: The times that shops are open (Wolfson et al., 2019).	Time availability & convenience: The time people have available to shop for and prepare food (especially for those in work, impoverished or parenting) (Beatty et al., 2013).
Amount and choice barriers: if there is enough available of the preferred food (Wolfson et al., 2019).	Infrastructure: Households can store and prepare food (especially for those housing insecure) (Clair et al., 2020).

Unfortunately, experiencing food insecurity doesn't only mean reduced or irregular eating; it also has a considerable effect on nutritional intake and related dietary health. Household food insecurity is regularly associated with the 'substitution effect', where high-quality, nutritious, less calorie-dense foods are substituted with cheaper, less varied, more convenient, less-nutritious, more calorie-dense options (higher simple carbohydrates, fats and added sugars) (Morales & Berkowitz, 2018).

The impact on dietary quality is associated with elevated markers of low-grade inflammation and diet-related chronic illness such as diabetes, metabolic syndrome, obesity and related impacts on mental health, such as psychological distress and diagnoses of depression and anxiety (Loopstra, 2018). Worryingly, children are highly impacted by such food security issues (see Box 1).

Box 1: How household food insecurity affects children

In comparison to the DWP's 11% household food insecurity rate in adults, over 30% of children are adversely affected due to the association of food insecurity with households with children (Goudie, 2023). Food insecurity can have a profoundly negative effect on young people, impacting mental and physical health & wellbeing and is associated with: chronic health issues (e.g., asthma), stunted growth, worsened behavioural and educational outcomes, poor social wellbeing, adolescent anxiety, depression & suicidal intention, among other impacts (Chambers et al., 2024). Interestingly, while parents have some success in shielding their children from the effects of household food insecurity (Power et al., 2021), youth-specific interventions have been inconsistent in alleviating symptoms of food insecurity (Mahdi et al., 2025). Successful youth-specific interventions could help prevent recurring food insecurity in adulthood (Dubois et al., 2023).

In response to these issues, there has been a huge increase in alternative food access models which enable a range of positive outcomes for individuals, households, communities and volunteers (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Examples of the benefits of improved access to food.

↑ food and nutrition availability, stability and security	↑ feelings of being needed and purposefulness for volunteers
↑ choice of healthy food and dietary health	↑ financial savings and well-being
↑ physical and mental well-being via consistent, secured healthy eating	↑ food resilience
↑ prevention outcomes (e.g., hospital admissions)	↓ short-term hunger and malnutrition
↑ food empowerment, autonomy and dignity where choice is built into the model	↓ at risk of chronic illnesses through dietary and behavioural change
↑ food knowledge, experience and literacy	↓ negative health outcomes
↑ food-related behaviour changes	↓ the proportion of household income spent on seeking nutritional security
↑ shopping and preparation practices	↓ feelings of exclusion and isolation

How do alternative food access models support communities?

It's estimated that community food aid initiatives may alleviate at least £22m worth of state spending on food welfare (when accounting for socially acceptable, consensual-based provision, upwards of £75m) (Caraher & Furey, 2018). This is before considering any potential cost savings associated with the prevention of food insecurity (e.g. over £20bn worth of healthcare spending on preventable dietary ill-health) (Lowe & Mahmood, 2022).

In grassroots food aid initiatives, there may also be cultural benefits, for example, exemplifying the reinforcement of social cohesion, communality and solidarity (Gomez Garrido et al., 2019). Environmentally, alternative access to food can strengthen local food systems, contributing to security, health, sustainability, justice and resilience, as well as potentially contributing to climate change mitigation (Papargyropoulou et al., 2024).

Why nutrition must be central in food aid

There is an agreement that food aid improves food security and diet quality that beneficiaries otherwise wouldn't experience (Oldroyd et al., 2022). However, there is growing evidence to suggest that food aid provisions exceed recommendations for carbohydrates, sugars, fats and salt and sometimes lack adequate protein, fibre, calcium, iron, folate, iodine, magnesium, potassium and vitamins A, C, D and E (Stahacz et al., 2024). This has the potential to drive beneficiaries into 'hidden hunger' (unseen lack of nutrients) and is associated with recurring food insecurity and repeated use of food aid initiatives (Burchi et al., 2011). Users are then failing to move up the food ladder towards independence and nutritional adequacy, and remaining reliant (Oldroyd et al., 2022).

Box 2: Defining nutritional security

Nutritional security is related to the ability to consistently and equitably access sufficient quantities and quality of food that meets an individual's nutritional needs (Jones et al., 2024). This ability to access adequate nutrition to meet individual needs is then a dimension of broader food security, which also factors in other dimensions (e.g., cultural or social norms) (Pérez-Escamilla, 2024).

Box 3: A bit about FareShare

The project was supported by FareShare, which is the UK's longest-running food redistribution charity, co-founded by homeless charity Crisis and Sainsbury's, made up of 18 independent organisations (social franchises) and operating across 21 regions nationally (FareShare, 2025). Nationally, last year, FareShare distributed around 57,000 tonnes of food, equating to an estimated four meals every second or 135 million meals and reaching almost one million individuals across 99% of the UK (FareShare, 2024). Of the food redistributed, 94% was good-to-eat surplus, preventing the emission of an estimated 106,000 tonnes of CO2 eq. and use of 141 billion litres of water (FareShare, 2024). FareShare plays a mediatory role in the redistribution of surplus food, where they arrange the logistics of collecting surplus at the manufacturing and retail stages and deliver it to food aid initiatives that distribute the food to in-need communities (Alexander & Smaje, 2008).

How was the research conducted?

This research aimed to help address the gap in understanding by identifying opportunities to enhance the nutritional security in food aid initiatives supported by surplus food supply.

Mapping the surplus food system: Insights from FareShare

Stage one involved learning how FareShare Yorkshire operates. This observation involved first-person inquiry of supply mechanisms, logistics, product organisation, and delivery, as well as initial interviews with FareShare Yorkshire and Yorkshire food aid charities in Barnsley, Sheffield, Leeds, and Greater Bradford. This stage was important for gaining high-quality experiential knowledge about the surplus food supply chain logistics, including identifying wider stakeholders, processes, and mechanisms involved.

What the evidence says: Scoping review

An initial internet search of key terms decided upon from stage one (e.g., 'surplus food redistribution', 'food aid', 'food insecurity'), a snowballing technique was used to identify relevant studies which discussed the challenges and opportunities within the system. Studies were screened for relevance using titles and abstracts before a further in-depth review. In essence, this was a system mapping exercise helping us to better understand the current landscape of household food insecurity, surplus food (re)distribution, alternative food access and nutrition & dietary health.

How was the research conducted?

Understanding the context: Survey with food aid settings

To gain a better understanding of the capacity of food aid initiatives to provision nutritional food, we shared an online survey to all subscribers of FareShare Yorkshire, food aid initiatives connected to North Yorkshire Council and through the FixOurFood LinkedIn page. A total of 40 settings responded to the survey.

Insights from the front line: Interviews with food aid initiatives

We interviewed representatives from food aid initiatives that use surplus food as part of their provision. FareShare Yorkshire facilitated connections with food aid initiatives across Yorkshire which they felt would provide diverse insights and represent a cross section of perspectives and approaches. In total, we interviewed 14 food aid initiatives. The research team also interviewed FareShare Yorkshire, in a dedicated focus group. These conversations concentrated on lived experiences and explored constraints and opportunities when trying to support the nutritional security of their beneficiaries.

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Why Yorkshire?

A regional case study

Yorkshire was selected for a case study as it's the geographic focus of the FixOurFood programme. Yorkshire also holds significance in the national food system, it supports 13-17% of the UK's crop production area, has a high diversity of soils and land cover and farming systems, and 10-14% of the nation's livestock headcount (including being home to 40% of the pig population) (Buckton et al., 2024). Yorkshire also contains the UK's largest concentration of food and drinks manufacturers (3,000+), with a combined economic value of over £3bn (Doherty et al., 2021).

At the same time, Yorkshire has a high prevalence of household food insecurity (20.6% in 2022), in some areas, this is at least 1.5x higher than the national average. There are also significant inequalities throughout the region (e.g., 1,000 in-need children go without free school meals in York compared with 14,000 in Bradford) (Ferguson, 2021). As such, Yorkshire is an ideal case-study region due to its unique food-related expertise and diverse landscape of food insecurity, access and assistance.

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Results of the scoping review

What does a review of literature tell us about nutritional security in food aid initiatives using surplus food?

The scoping review showed that surplus food (re)distribution - alternative food access is highly dynamic, and both enabled and constrained among many scales. Findings confirmed the importance of taking a more systemic view of the relationship between surplus food (re)distribution, alternative food access and nutritional security. Several key challenges and opportunities were identified through this process; these are summarised below.

Challenges

Insufficient to meet needs

It's widely agreed that in its current form, surplus food is insufficient in addressing long-term nutritional needs because of issues with quality and availability (i.e. McIntyre et al., 2016; Thompson et al., 2018; Fallaize et al., 2020; Berri & Toma, 2022).

Inaccessibility of settings

There are many factors that limit the accessibility of food assistance. This can be due to both operating times or distance, which can affect those who are disabled, socially isolated or without transport (Lambie-Mumford & Sims, 2018; Loopstra et al., 2019; Price et al., 2020; Mikelbank, 2021).

Feelings of shame

Food aid users have described a sense of indignity associated with accepting aid, which can deter food-insecure individuals and households from seeking aid in the first place. This can be compounded by having to justify needs to gain access (Beck & Gwilym, 2020). Because of these issues food insecure people can experience feelings of failure, shame and embarrassment (Slocombe, 2023)

Institutionalisation of food aid

One of the most pressing challenges cited in research is the institutionalisation of food charities and wider commodification of care (McIntyre et al., 2016). This is because institutionalisation can turn initiatives into pseudo-markets, which then have to compete for resources (volunteers, food, funding, spaces, facilities, additional services, etc).

Results of the scoping review

Opportunities

Improvements to food security

Existing research suggests that, fundamentally, nearly all food aid initiatives do what they set out to do, which is provide emergency food relief to reduce hunger (Oldroyd et al., 2022).

Additional services

Research shows that initiatives which provide benefits 'beyond food' are better able to influence nutritional security (Thompson et al., 2018; Stahacz et al., 2024). However, it's also recognised that resources to support wider activities aren't always available.

Sustainable approaches

Research advocates for market-like models (e.g., cafe, social supermarket) as they increase financial stability of initiatives and help beneficiaries work towards food independence (Nayak & Hartwell, 2023; Stahacz et al., 2024; McEachern et al., 2024).

Social opportunities

Research demonstrates that the process of receiving food aid can support social inclusion, community cohesion and a sense of belonging. This can contribute to positive health outcomes (both physical and mental) (Wainwright et al., 2018; Taylor et al., 2024).

Results from the survey

What did a survey tell us about the barriers, enablers and aspirations for food aid initiatives providing nutrition?

Why did food aid initiatives start?

Findings from the survey demonstrate that food aid providers are deeply motivated by a commitment to community wellbeing, dignity, and justice. Many initiatives were born in response to urgent need, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic and the subsequent rise in the cost of living. They have since evolved into sustained efforts to support local people facing hardship. Food aid initiatives emphasised the importance of ensuring that no one in their community goes hungry, that surplus food is not wasted, and that individuals can access food in a way that preserves their dignity.

Some framed their work as a response to gaps in government provision, while others described a desire to create warm, welcoming spaces that go beyond food to offer connection, support, and care. Faith groups, volunteers, and people with lived experience of hardship were central to founding many of these initiatives, highlighting a strong ethic of mutual aid and local responsibility. Across the responses, there was a clear sense of purpose: to alleviate immediate hunger, reduce waste, and build inclusive, resilient communities through food.

What are the barriers to providing nutritious food?

Several barriers were identified by food aid initiatives, these were largely related to supply and infrastructure (see Table 2).

Table 2. Barriers to providing nutritious food in food aid initiatives.

Examples of barriers	Supporting quotes
Food providers cannot plan balanced meals due to variability.	<i>"We are reliant on what is available from our suppliers, and we don't know until we receive the delivery what we will have."</i>
Donated food may be close to expiry or nutritionally limited.	<i>"Supermarkets give out OOD [out of date] food too late and we find it is often not fit to feed people."</i>
Lack of funding, staffing, and physical resources restricts nutrition-related initiatives.	<i>"Yes, lack of human, physical and financial assets and resources." "Due to the high amount of people we support we sometimes run out of food."</i>
Fresh food cannot be safely stored, leading to waste.	<i>"We provide nutritionally balanced food, but many of our members are unable to store it because they don't have refrigeration and so often food goes to waste."</i>
Some recipients struggle to prepare meals with the food provided.	<i>"Inability of some customers to cook either because they don't know how to or have to balance putting the washing machine on versus cooking a family meal."</i>
Some donated food items are overly processed or not culturally appropriate.	<i>"Some of the food (particularly vegan) we donate can be very processed."</i>

Results from the survey

What helps food aid initiatives to provision nutritious food?

Despite many of the challenges faced, food aid initiatives used a range of methods to help increase their nutritional offering (see Table 3).

Table 3. Actions that support better nutrition delivery from food aid settings.

Example	Supporting quotes
Grants and donations allow providers to buy fresh or missing items.	<p><i>"Some individual donations allow us to purchase eggs and milk and some additional fruit and veg."</i></p> <p><i>"We use additional funding to ensure we can do this."</i></p>
Providers tailor parcels with fresh, frozen, and ambient foods.	<i>"Each parcel is made up to suit the person's unique needs... we give a well-balanced parcel."</i>
Offering fruit and veg routinely, even when donations are limited.	<i>"We offer free fruit and veg to everyone."</i>
Working with FareShare Yorkshire and other suppliers, and topping up when needed.	<p><i>"FareShare products plus what we buy in to accommodate this [providing nutrition]."</i></p> <p><i>"Communicating with FareShare [to give food preferences]."</i></p>
Cold storage enables providers to preserve a wider variety of healthy food.	<i>"[Nutritious food can be provided by] Having capacity to store chilled and frozen food, as well as ambient stock."</i>
Workshops and resources support long-term healthy eating.	<p><i>"We run diet and nutrition workshops working with local GPs."</i></p> <p><i>"Training in food preparation and common sense."</i></p>
Meals reflect diverse diets and preferences, often unintentionally through surplus.	<i>"Our food is always a range of dishes, ingredients, flavours and from many cultures."</i>
Recipe cards and ingredients make it easier to cook nutritious meals.	<i>"Recipe cards and ingredients designed by a chef for easy but nutritious food."</i>
Hot meals provide immediate support and model nutritious eating.	<i>"Breakfast and hot lunches provided plus some fresh vegetables to take away."</i>

Results from the survey

What are the aspirations for the future?

Food aid providers are working towards a future where they can respond to rising needs while improving the quality, dignity, and sustainability of their support. Their aspirations include both strengthening immediate provision and reducing long-term reliance on food aid through community-led, inclusive approaches.

Key aspirations include:

- Meeting rising demand with consistently nutritious, balanced food parcels.
- Securing ongoing donations and funding to maintain essential services.
- Expanding infrastructure (e.g. storage, cold chain, kitchen facilities).
- Increasing staff and volunteer capacity to deliver wraparound support.
- Reaching households who may be reluctant to seek help.
- Offering practical support such as cooking classes, recipe cards, and digital tools.
- Using surplus food creatively in cafés and community meals.
- Shifting from emergency provision to sustainable, empowering models.
- Supporting people to move on from food aid and into greater food security.
- Building a future in which food aid is no longer needed, and nutritious food is accessible to all.

Results from the survey

Barriers to achieving aspirations?

Food aid initiatives face a range of barriers that limit their ability to expand, improve, or sustain nutritional support, with funding insecurity and capacity challenges being the most frequently raised concerns.

Key barriers include:

- Short-term, uncertain funding streams, including the possible loss of the Household Support Fund.
- Rising cost of living may reduce donations from the public and businesses.
- Inadequate cold storage facilities and increased energy costs impacting food handling.
- Difficulty recruiting and retaining skilled staff or volunteers to coordinate and deliver services.
- Time and resource pressures limiting the ability to plan or innovate.
- Increasing community need outpacing available support.
- Structural poverty and inequality, which food aid cannot resolve alone.
- Rural location and transport costs create barriers to access and service delivery.
- Stigma associated with receiving food aid prevents some households from seeking support.
- A lack of long-term, joined-up policy solutions that recognise the scale and emotional labour of food aid work.

Statistics:

68% predict an increase in the need for food aid in the next 3 years

46% of initiatives feel they provide nutritious food consistently, **46%** feel they can sometimes, **4%** felt they consistently were not able to provide this and **4%** were unsure.

Results from interviews

What are the challenges and opportunities for nutritional food security in food aid initiatives?

Challenges for nutritional food security include:

Limited choice in donated food items

While some initiatives source food alternatively (i.e., buying, growing, etc), there is rarely much control over the food that could be received as donations. This is compounded by a *“fear that rejecting stock might hinder relationships with suppliers/donors and limit what might be received in the future,”* and feeling like *“there isn’t enough money to afford to reject donations.”*

Barriers to utilisation in the home

Some nutritious foods are not distributed by food aid initiatives due to a range of factors. Cultural preferences can play a role, for example, some older beneficiaries may prefer traditional meals and be less open to unfamiliar ingredients. A lack of adequate equipment, such as fridges or cooking facilities, can prevent households from safely storing or preparing fresh produce. In some cases, recipients may be unfamiliar with certain foods and unsure how to use them. Personal preferences and the desire for control over food choices may also lead to items being declined. Finally, safety concerns can arise when surplus foods are close to their use-by date.

Limited storage capacity in food aid initiatives

There is often a lack of adequate facilities (e.g., a freezer) to safely store and offer certain foods. This has consequences upstream in supply, which can be perceived as a low demand for some ‘healthy’ products. Essentially, while past research frames some of the challenges associated with aid-distributed food as an issue flowing from the top-down (sourced upstream in supply), there are also significant challenges developing from the bottom-up that limit the capacity to receive fresh produce.

Lack of human resources

Food aid initiatives require a diverse skills base, this might include knowledge or procurement systems, health and safety, relationship building, finance management, cooking skills, basic food preparation. But there are limited resources to support the training and development of volunteers.

Nutrition not the priority

Because of the high demand for emergency food relief, nutritional security is not outlined as a key target. Beneficiaries themselves might be facing significant social challenges which take precedent over nutrition.

Results from interviews

What are the challenges and opportunities for nutritional food security in food aid initiatives?

Opportunities for nutritional food security include:

Moderating supply of 'unhealthy' foods

Highly-processed, longer shelf life, 'unhealthy' foods are often "drip fed" into food aid initiatives by FareShare Yorkshire so that parcels or pantry options remain nutritionally balanced. Some initiatives use these products (i.e. chocolates) in other ways, such as raffle prizes to raise additional funds. While these foods aren't necessarily ideal for nutrition and health, redistribution means that beneficiaries can spend their money on other items.

Outsourcing logistics

FareShare Yorkshire's logistical & networking capabilities mean that they can consistently and efficiently source, organise and (re)distribute surplus food at a fraction of commercial costs. This means that those who work with FareShare Yorkshire have been able to reduce time and costs. Resources can then be reallocated to source more produce and provide wrap around services such as financial advice or cooking skills. FareShare Yorkshire also sources non-food tangibles such as facilities and infrastructure (e.g., fridges) and intangibles such as contacts (i.e., facilitating relationship building), often informally. However, not all food aid initiatives were aware of this.

Applying multiple approaches to providing food aid

A mixed model approach to food aid provision was used across many food aid initiatives. This meant that emergency food aid was accessible to those who needed it most (e.g., food banks and kitchens for homeless peoples). But at the same time, pantries or social supermarket models were available to those who have some accessible funds. This meant that people could move up the food ladder as appropriate.

Diverse procurement

Some food aid initiatives put considerable effort into exploring different strategies for procuring resources, which increased their resilience and capacity to keep delivering food aid. This involved using services such as Caboodle and TooGoodToGo as well as cultivating relationships with local greengrocers or butchers. Those with capacity are even experimenting with growing foods such as veg gardens, community allotments, with some experimenting with setting up vertical aeroponic farms.

Results from interviews

Maintaining volunteer capacity

Some initiatives use services such as Neighbourly to source volunteers who wish to donate their time to in-need organisations. This helps to ensure enough ground support to deliver essential service.

Committed volunteers

Another setting talked about the value of having long serving volunteers who showed dedication through personal donations, offering fridge/freezer spaces to store fresh foods and cooking. Some programmes are fortunate to have someone with skills and experience in developing funding applications.

Experiential learning

An active, participatory approach to education, such as cooking classes or recipe demonstrations was found to be much more effective in engaging beneficiaries to improve confidence and skills, ultimately leading to healthier diets and positive health outcomes. More passive forms of education, such recipe cards were found to be less effective.

Eatwell guidance

One initiative that we spoke with arranged the pantry in the style of the Eatwell plate (i.e., proteins, carbs, fats, etc., as opposed to tins, packaged foods). Another uses a point system for access to the products in the pantry and gives 'unhealthy' foods more points (essentially making them more expensive than 'healthy' foods). These small changes orientate the beneficiary provisions towards healthier foods in a subtle and non-intrusive way.

Results from interviews

Demonstrating care

Many services spoke about the importance of demonstrating care (i.e., knowing people’s names and stories) to develop an atmosphere of trust and respect. This means beneficiaries are more likely to share their needs with volunteers. Ultimately this could help volunteers to understand barriers to nutrition and help them to source the most appropriate foods.

Supportive networks

Food aid initiatives were found to share cooking equipment, fridges & freezers, vans and potentially even funding (through joint funding bids for greater community impact). Networks extended to other service food aid initiatives, such as finance advisors and employment support.

Table 4. Key difference between the literature review and research findings

Theme	Literature review findings	Research findings
Nutrition as a priority	Emphasises the importance of improving diet quality and reducing hidden hunger. Food aid often lacks essential nutrients.	Nutrition is acknowledged but usually not prioritised due to more urgent needs (e.g., hunger relief, crisis support).
Barriers to provision	Focus on systemic issues (e.g., austerity, structural inequality, institutionalisation).	Focus on operational challenges (e.g., lack of fridges, volunteer shortages, unpredictable supply).
Wraparound services	Identified as best practice for supporting long-term food independence and well-being.	Some are offering these services informally; others lack resources to implement them.
Use of surplus food	Critiqued as nutritionally inconsistent, with limited value as a long-term solution.	Practitioners make strategic use of surplus, managing “unhealthy” foods thoughtfully and creatively.

Conclusion and recommendations

Food aid initiatives play a vital role in supporting individuals and families facing food insecurity across the UK. They do more than alleviate immediate hunger, they offer connection, care, and a sense of dignity in times of crisis. As household food insecurity continues to rise, these community-led efforts have become essential lifelines, especially in areas of entrenched poverty or inequality.

Surplus food plays a significant part in enabling these initiatives. Mediatory organisations like FareShare Yorkshire reduce the operational burden of food aid initiatives through logistical and practical support. As a key part of the food aid system, FareShare Yorkshire recognised that there are constraints to providing adequate nutrition in surplus food supply chains. As a result, they initiated this research to explore ways to enable better nutrition from several different aspects of the food aid system.

This report has drawn from literature, survey findings, and interviews with practitioners to understand what works and where support is most needed. The following recommendations are grounded in this evidence and explore nutrition through a whole system lens (see Table 5).

Table 5. Recommendations for creating conditions for better nutritional security.

Stakeholder	Recommendation	Description
Policymakers	Make nutritional security a strategic priority	Embed nutritional outcomes into local and national food policies and ensure they are measurable. This will help to ensure that health and well-being becomes a focus in policy planning.
	Support dignified food access models	Support community pantries, social supermarkets, and cafés through supportive planning and regulation to ensure that there are appropriate models of food aid access that help beneficiaries work towards food independence.
	Link food aid with wraparound services	Facilitate integration with health, housing, and financial support to address root causes of nutritional insecurity.
Funders	Provide long term, flexible funding	Enable food aid initiatives to plan sustainably, retain staff, and build local capacity. This will help create stability in services and capacity to source nutritious food.
	Fund programmes that improve food literacy	Support cooking classes, nutrition education, and community food skills development through experiential learning. This will help to build skills and confidence when using fresh produce.
	Promote collaboration across organisations	Encourage joint bids and shared learning to improve resilience and impact across services that aim to reduce poverty and food insecurity. This will help to build collaborative capacity and ensure a more rounded approach to tackling nutritional insecurity.
	Invest in essential food infrastructure	Fund cold storage, kitchen space, and transport, especially in under-resourced areas. This will mean that food aid initiatives can accept and distribute more fresh foods.

Conclusion and recommendations

Stakeholder	Recommendation	Description
Surplus food suppliers	Improve nutritional quality of food supply	Increase access to fresh, frozen, and high protein items while reducing ultra processed donations by creating feedback reports that show nutrition delivered by individual donors.
	Communicate clearly with food aid initiatives	Share updates on services so that food aid initiatives know the full breadth of what is available.
	Respond to cultural and dietary needs	Distribute surplus that better reflects diverse communities and avoids inappropriate waste. This will ensure that the preferable types of nutritious food are more accessible.
	Enable feedback from food aid initiatives	Create channels to feedback on food quality and appropriateness and adjust order distributions based on feedback. Develop an award system that shows the nutritional quality of foods donated by major donors.
Food aid initiatives	Use blended access models	Combine emergency food provision with social supermarkets or pantries to promote dignity and choice.
	Embed nutrition in service design	Use food layouts, signage, and educational resources to promote healthy eating practices.
	Advocate for support to increase food skills	Integrate hands-on support like cooking classes and nutrition workshops into service delivery to increase people's capacity to use different types of nutritious food that they are less familiar with.
	Strengthen relationships and inclusion	Foster welcoming, culturally sensitive spaces that build trust, dignity, and peer support. This relationship building aspect will help to reduce stigma and ensure better access to food aid services.

Conclusion and recommendations

What next?

This report highlights the many ways food aid initiatives are evolving from short-term emergency responses into embedded community services. With this transition, there is growing potential to recognise them not just as providers of food, but as hubs for improving social, health and well-being outcomes.

However, several gaps remain. Children are disproportionately affected by food insecurity, yet they were not a strong focus in our findings. To support long term nutritional health, we should ask how food aid initiatives can become more inclusive of children. This might mean that settings create family friendly spaces for learning about growing, preparing and cooking foods in creative ways.

There is also potential for more joined up support with public health. Food aid initiatives have created trusted spaces with often hard to reach communities that could also benefit from more accessible health support. Developing these connections mean that food aid initiatives play a more central role in preventative health care.

Recognising food aid initiatives as part of the wider public health landscape invites new conversations about partnerships and funding. These questions represent a crucial next step in understanding how food aid can support not just food access, but healthier and more resilient communities. Ultimately, this may reframe how food aid initiatives are conceptualised, thereby reducing stigma and increasing overall accessibility.

References

Alexander, C., & Smaje, C. (2008). Surplus retail food redistribution: An analysis of a third sector model. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 52(11), 1290-1298.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2008.07.009>

Beatty, T. K., Nanney, M. S., & Tuttle, C. (2013). Time to eat? The relationship between food security and food-related time use. *Public Health Nutrition*, 17(1), 66-72.

<https://doi.org/10.1017/s1368980012005599>

Beck, D., & Gwilym, H. (2020). The moral maze of foodbank use. *Journal of Poverty and Social Justice*, 28(3). <https://doi.org/10.1332/175982720x15905998909942>

Berri, A., & Toma, L. (2023). Factors influencing consumer use of social supermarkets in the UK: A redistribution model providing low-cost surplus food. *Cleaner and Responsible Consumption*, 10, 100133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clrc.2023.100133>

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clrc.2023.100133>

Bose, P. S. (2024). Getting people to food and food to people: considering transportation barriers and food access in the future of food. *Geographical Review*, 115(1-2), 1-21.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/00167428.2024.2383459>

Boyle, N. B., & Power, M. (2023). Proxy longitudinal indicators of household food insecurity in the UK. *Emerald Open Research*, 1(10). <https://doi.org/10.1108/eor-10-2023-0009>

Buckton, S. J., Ioan Fazey, Doherty, B., Bryant, M., Banwart, S. A., Carmen, E., ... Cordero, J. P. (2024). Transformative action towards regenerative food systems: A large-scale case study. *PLOS Sustainability and Transformation*, 3(11), e0000134-e0000134. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pstr.0000134>

Burchi, F., Fanzo, J., & Frison, E. (2011). The Role of Food and Nutrition System Approaches in Tackling Hidden Hunger. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 8(2), 358-373.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph8020358>

Caraher, M., & Furey, S. (2018). Food Banks and Their Contribution/Detraction from Welfare Budgets. *SpringerLink*, 73-90. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-78506-6_4

Chambers, S., Machray, K., & Fergie, G. (2024). Food insecurity in children and young people in Scotland. *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, 83(3), 1-32. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0029665124000090>

Clair, A., Fledderjohann, J., Lalor, D., & Loopstra, R. (2019). The Housing Situations of Food Bank Users in Great Britain. *Social Policy and Society*, 19(1), 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s1474746419000150>

Devine, B. F., Harari, D., Keep, M., Bolton, P., Barton, C., Harker, R., & Cromarty, H. (2024). Rising cost of living in the UK. *House of Commons Library*. Retrieved from:

<https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/cbp-9428/>

References

Doherty, B., Bryant, M., Denby, K. J., Ioan Fazey, Bridle, S., Hawkes, C., ... Yap, C. (2021). Transformations to regenerative food systems—An outline of the FixOurFood project. *Nutrition Bulletin*, 47(1), 106–114. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nbu.12536>

Douglas, F. (2023). What qualitative research can tell us about food and nutrition security in the UK and why we should pay attention to what it's telling us. *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, 83(3), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0029665123003713>

Dubois, L., Bédard, B., Goulet, D., Prud'homme, D., Tremblay, R. E., & Boivin, M. (2023). Experiencing food insecurity in childhood: influences on eating habits and body weight in young adulthood. *Public Health Nutrition*, 26(11), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s1368980023001854>

Fallaize, R., Newlove, J., White, A., & Lovegrove, J. A. (2020). Nutritional adequacy and content of food bank parcels in Oxfordshire, UK: a comparative analysis of independent and organisational provision. *Journal of Human Nutrition and Dietetics*, 33(4), 477–486. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jhn.12740>

FareShare. (2024). FareShare's Impact Report 2024: *Transforming surplus food into support*. Retrieved from <https://fareshare.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/Impact-report-2024-condensed.pdf>

FareShare. (2025). Fighting hunger, Tackling Food Waste in the UK. Retrieved from FareShare website: <https://fareshare.org.uk/>

Ferguson, R. (2021, July 22). New map shows where millions of UK residents struggle to access food. Retrieved July 24, 2025, from The University of Sheffield website: <https://sheffield.ac.uk/news/new-map-shows-where-millions-uk-residents-struggle-access-food>

Francis-Devine, B. (2024, April 8). Who is experiencing food insecurity in the UK? Retrieved from House of Commons Library website: <https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/who-is-experiencing-food-insecurity-in-the-uk/>

Gómez Garrido, M., Carbonero Gamundí, M. A., & Viladrich, A. (2018). The role of grassroots food banks in building political solidarity with vulnerable people. *European Societies*, 21(5), 753–773. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616696.2018.1518537>

Goudie, S. (2023, March 1). Child food insecurity doubles fueling calls for urgent expansion of Free School Meals | Food Foundation. Retrieved from foodfoundation.org.uk website: <https://foodfoundation.org.uk/publication/child-food-insecurity-doubles-fueling-calls-urgent-expansion-free-school-meals>

Hardcastle, S. J., & Caraher, M. (2021). The role of foodbanks in the context of food insecurity: Experiences and eating behaviours amongst users. *Appetite*, 163, 105208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2021.105208>

References

- Jones, S. M., Anvari, S., Coleman, A., Pesek, R. D., Kloepfer, K. M., Perry, T. T., ... Scurlock, A. M. (2023). Food insecurity and allergic diseases: A call to collective action. *Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology*, 153(2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaci.2023.10.019>
- Lambie-Mumford, H., & Sims, L. (2018). "Feeding Hungry Children": The Growth of Charitable Breakfast Clubs and Holiday Hunger Projects in the UK. *Children & Society*, 32(3), 244-254. <https://doi.org/10.1111/chso.12272>
- Loopstra, R. (2018). Interventions to Address Household Food Insecurity in high-income Countries. *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, 77(3), 270-281. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s002966511800006x>
- Loopstra, R., Lambie-Mumford, H., & Fledderjohann, J. (2019). Food Bank Operational Characteristics and Rates of Food Bank Use across Britain. *BMC Public Health*, 19(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-019-6951-6>
- Lowe, R., & Mahmood, H. (2022, October 21). Why preventing food insecurity will support the NHS and save lives | NHS Confederation. Retrieved from <https://www.nhsconfed.org/long-reads/why-preventing-food-insecurity-will-support-nhs-and-save-lives>
- Mahdi, S., Connolly, A., Doherty, B., & Bryant, M. (2025). "Will my fingerprint be enough?": Secondary school students struggle to purchase a healthy, tasty and sustainable meal on the UK free school meal allowance. *Public Health Nutrition*, 28(1), 1-25. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1368980024002593>
- McEachern, M. G., Moraes, C., Scullion, L., & Gibbons, A. (2024). Urban poverty and the role of UK food aid organisations in enabling segregating and transitioning spaces of food access. *Urban Studies*, 61(11), 2231-2249. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00420980241234803>
- McIntyre, L., Tougas, D., Rondeau, K., & Mah, C. L. (2016). "In"-sights about food banks from a critical interpretive synthesis of the academic literature. *Agriculture and Human Values*, 33(4), 843-859. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10460-015-9674-z>
- Mikelbank, B. A. (2021). Spatial, Temporal, and Transit Access to Emergency Food Providers. *The Professional Geographer*, 73(4), 725-736. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00330124.2021.1934881>
- Morales, M. E., & Berkowitz, S. A. (2016). The Relationship Between Food Insecurity, Dietary Patterns, and Obesity. *Current Nutrition Reports*, 5(1), 54-60. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13668-016-0153-y>
- Nayak, R., & Hartwell, H. (2023). The future of charitable alternative food networks in the UK: an investigation into current challenges and opportunities for foodbanks and community markets. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2023.1187015>

References

- Oldroyd, L., Eskandari, F., Pratt, C., & Lake, A. (2022). The Nutritional Quality of Food Parcels Provided by Foodbanks and the Effectiveness of Foodbanks at Reducing Food Insecurity in Developed countries: a Mixed-method Systematic Review. *Journal of Human Nutrition and Dietetics*, 35(6).
<https://doi.org/10.1111/jhn.12994>
- Papargyropoulou, E., Bridge, G., Woodcock, S., Strachan, E., Rowlands, J., & Boniface, E. (2024). Impact of food hubs on food security and sustainability: Food hubs perspectives from Leeds, UK. *Food Policy*, 128, 102705–102705. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2024.102705>
- Pérez-Escamilla, R. (2024). Food and nutrition security definitions, constructs, frameworks, measurements, and applications: global lessons. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 12.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2024.1340149>
- Power, M., Pybus, K. J., Pickett, K. E., & Doherty, B. (2021). “The reality is that on Universal Credit I cannot provide the recommended amount of fresh fruit and vegetables per day for my children”: moving from a behavioural to a systemic understanding of food practices. *Emerald Open Research*, 1(10).
<https://doi.org/10.1108/eor-10-2023-0007>
- Price, C., Barons, M., Garthwaite, K., & Jolly, A. (2020). “The Do-Gooders and Scroungers”: Examining Narratives of Foodbank Use in Online Local Press Coverage in the West Midlands, UK. *Journal of Poverty and Social Justice*, 28(3). <https://doi.org/10.1332/175982720x15905998323834>
- Slocombe, H. (2023). Aged spaces in an era of austerity: Food bank use by older people. *Area*, 55(3).
<https://doi.org/10.1111/area.12870>
- Stahacz, C., Alwan, N. A., Taylor, E., Smith, D., & Ziauddeen, N. (2024). The impact of food aid interventions on food insecurity, diet quality and mental health in households with children in high-income countries: a systematic review. *Public Health Nutrition*, 27(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1017/s1368980024001769>
- Stone, R. A., Brown, A., Douglas, F., Green, M. A., Hunter, E., Lonnie, M., ... FIO-Food Team. (2024). The impact of the cost of living crisis and food insecurity on food purchasing behaviours and food preparation practices in people living with obesity. *Appetite*, 196(196), 107255.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2024.107255>
- Strong, S. (2021). Facing hunger, framing food banks, imaging austerity. *Social & Cultural Geography*, 23(9), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14649365.2021.1921247>
- Taylor, N., Boyland, E., & Hardman, C. A. (2024). Conceptualising food banking in the UK from drivers of use to impacts on health and wellbeing: a systematic review and directed content analysis. *Appetite*, 203, 107699–107699. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2024.107699>

References

The Food Foundation. (2024). Food Insecurity Tracking. Retrieved from foodfoundation.org.uk website: <https://foodfoundation.org.uk/initiatives/food-insecurity-tracking#tabs/Overview-of-surveys->

Thompson, C., Smith, D., & Cummins, S. (2018). Understanding the health and wellbeing challenges of the food banking system: A qualitative study of food bank users, providers and referrers in London. *Social Science & Medicine*, 211(1), 95-101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2018.05.030>

Wainwright, D., Buckingham, A., & Wainwright, E. (2018). Why do people use food banks? A qualitative study of food bank users in an English city. *Voluntary Sector Review*, 9(3), 311-329. <https://doi.org/10.1332/204080518x15428930047072>

Westwater, H., & McRae, I. (2023, May 2). Food poverty in the UK: The causes, figures and solutions. Retrieved from The Big Issue website: <https://www.bigissue.com/news/social-justice/food-poverty-in-the-uk-the-causes-figures-and-solutions/>

Wolfson, J. A., Ramsing, R., Richardson, C. R., & Palmer, A. (2019). Barriers to healthy food access: Associations with household income and cooking behavior. *Preventive Medicine Reports*, 13(1), 298-305. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmedr.2019.01.023>

Yau, A., White, M., Hammond, D., White, C., & Adams, J. (2020). Socio-demographic characteristics, diet and health among food insecure UK adults: cross-sectional analysis of the International Food Policy Study. *Public Health Nutrition*, 23(14), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s1368980020000087>